

**DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ORIGIN OF ARTERIAL
HYPERTENSION IN THE FARMING POPULATION
(EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SURVEY RESULTS)**

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The purpose of the research is to study and evaluate the epidemiological details of arterial hypertension (AG) in the population engaged in farming activities (FA).

Research material and methods. The population of farmers working in Fergana Valley of Uzbekistan (2182 representative group of men and women > 18-70 years old) was involved in a special epidemiological study and was studied. Questionnaire, clinical, biochemical and instrumental examination methods were used. Questionnaire, clinical, biochemical and instrumental examination methods were used. Arterial hypertension was diagnosed and evaluated according to the criteria recommended by the World Health Organization.

Research results and conclusions. In the population of farmers, Arterial Hypertension is diagnosed with a prevalence of 12.9% and a 3.5-fold difference in family social status ($p < 0.01$). In men, the influence of social factors is significantly stronger than in women. Arterial hypertension with a relatively high prevalence is confirmed in the population of people with higher education and engaged in family farming. Arterial Hypertension is observed with a prevalence of 14.6% in men and 11.3% in women. 31.3% of cases occur in different age groups, the frequency of its detection increases 6.4 times with age { $RR = 1.29\%$; 95%, $CI = 1.0\% - 1.66$; $\chi^2 = 5.19$; $p = 0.023$ }. The highest frequency of arterial hypertension diagnosis (19.7%) is confirmed in 50-69-year-olds. The frequency of low detection with a significant difference is 18-30 (6.9%) and ($p < 0.05$) of the population engaged in farming activities. It is observed in age groups (10.8%) ($p < 0.05$).